

Enhancing physical properties of wood through Lignin-Based Treatments

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Recent advancements in wood modification techniques are focused on enhancing the inherent quality of natural timber. To accomplish this goal, the use of biobased ingredients and treatments with a minimal environmental impact is preferred. As a result, researchers are constantly working on developing new solutions that ensure long-lasting properties and functionality, while reducing the risk of product failure.

This study presents the findings of the effects of impregnating various lignin solutions on the physical and surface properties of wood such as dimensional stability, wettability, and UV resistance. By improving these three essential properties simultaneously, it is expected that the wood's aesthetic appearance as well as its performance will be enhanced, making it suitable for various applications, including outdoor environments.

Results:

Visual appearance of samples before and after UV- radiation test.

Physical properties of samples

Specimen	WPG [%]*	Absorption Dose [%]	MC (65% RH–25 °C) [%]	Density [kg/m3]*	Increase in Density [%]
Pine Ref	-	-	8.49 (0.37)	437.84 (13.67)	-
Pine-L	2.15 (0.27)	10.38	8.07 (0.32)	450.22 (13.87)	2.14
Pine-AL	2.09 (0.20)	9.80	7.53 (0.24)	444.27 (15.12)	2.09
Pine-LNPs	1.98 (0.28)	9.84	7.80(0.25)	445.84 (11.84)	1.89

Conclusions: Three types of lignin were used as an active compound for wood treatment with the objective of improving its dimensional stability, wettability, and resistance to UV radiation. Impregnation of wood with acetylated lignin was the most effective for improving wood hygroscopic properties. Wood treated with acetylated lignin exhibited higher water contact angle and surface free energy. All proposed modifications improve resistance against UV radiation.

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